

Eurodoc endorses the Initiative for Science in Europe's new statement "ISE main recommendations towards Framework Programme 10"

ISE, the Initiative for Science in Europe, released the following statement "ISE's main recommendations towards Framework Programme 10" on 27.02.2025. On behalf of Eurodoc, the administrative board of Eurodoc endorses this statement.

The Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE) is an independent association bringing together European learned societies and scientific research organisations operating throughout all disciplines and across all research sectors. ISE has a history of being instrumental in promoting disruptive excellence-based funding programmes for scientific research and played a central role in the creation of the European Research Council (ERC). In the statement ISE highlights the importance of both the ERC and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)

*Two programmes, the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) and the European Research Council (ERC), each with different yet complementary objectives and criteria, have demonstrated their exceptional ability to **identify and promote excellence in Europe**.*

They are the only programmes currently funding bottom-up, curiosity-driven, and ground-breaking research at the frontier of knowledge. Both **produce new knowledge** and have **yielded usable outcomes and unexpected economic and social benefits**.¹

In Eurodoc, we share ISE's sentiments about the importance of a strong Framework Programme 10 and thus endorse ISE's statement. We encourage our collaborators and other stakeholders to do similarly.

Prepared by

This statement was prepared by representative in the ISE working group Linnea Carlsson (0000-0002-7123-3173) on Horizon Europe and Eurodoc's President Pil Maria Saugmann (0000-0002-3548-0134)

Signed by

President: Pil Maria Saugmann (0000-0002-3548-0134), Vice-president: Nicola Dengo (0000-0003-2534-7265), Treasure: Manca Lunder (0009-0005-4249-3979), Secretary: Hannah Schoch (0000-0002-3987-4106), General board members: Norbert Bencze (0000-0001-7108-5329), Karl Kilbo Edlund (0000-0001-7586-4119), Magali Weissgerber, (0000-0002-2999-055X)

Date of Publication: 11.03.2025

Contact: Eurodoc Board board@eurodoc.net

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

¹ https://initiative-se.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/25_02_27_ISE_FP10-Main_recommendations.pdf